

About the Taxonomic List of Heteroptera Collection in Zoological Museum of Gazi University (ZMGU), Ankara-Türkiye

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ABSTRACT: In the Zoology Museum of Gazi University(ZMGU) has a collection of Türkiye by a variety of insect groups.

In this paper is given presented list of suboder Heteroptera collection of this Museum, and this collection maintains much more than 381 species-group taxa belonging to 30 families.

In the collection includes aquatic, semi-aquatic and terrestrial specimens of Heteroptera specimens, they are also important part of the ZMGU- collection.

The collection material of Heteroptera was mostly stored in insect cases as pinned dry specimens or alcohol jars.

KEY WORDS: Heteroptera, collection, species list, Türkiye, zoological museum, Gazi University

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Professor Dr. Ahmet Koçak, who passed away in 2021, the founder of the Zoology Museum of Gazi University, has studied the insect fauna of Türkiye and many parts of the world since 1967.

He has published many scientific articles on these topics. He represented the lepidopterist field and was an international expert in his field.

There are thousands of specimens in the Heteroptera Collection at Gazi University Zoology Museum (ZMGU).

There is also a collection of various insect groups from Türkiye in this museum.

In the Türkiye Heteroptera fauna was included at least 1540 species/subspecies belonging to 420 genera of 40 families (Önder, et al., 2006; (Önder, et al., 2006; Dursun et al, 2010; Fent et al. 2010; Fent et al. 2011; Kıyak & Akar 2010; Çerçi & Dursun, 2017; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Özgen & Çerçi, 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Çerçi et al., 2019, 2020, 2021; Çerçi & Koçak, 2017; Çerçi, 2021; Çerçi & Tezcan, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi & Oruz, 2021).

The Heteroptera (Hemipera) Collection of Zoological Museum of Gazi (ZMGU) contains, 381 species/subspecies identified belonging to 204 genera of 30 Heteroptera families.

In the collection includes aquatic, semi-aquatic and terrestrial of Heteroptera specimens.

The collection material of ZMGU is mostly stored in insect cases as pinned dry specimens.

In addition, a considerable proportion of the specimens is stored in alcohol-jars – the most comprehensive entomological collection at the zoological museum of Gazi University.

The collection has with a geographical focus on Türkiye insect fauna.

Furthermore, there are many specimens from Kosovo in the collection.

History:

The oldest pieces of the collection are over 35 years old, dating back to the time the Zoological Museum was founded.

The collection is scientifically invaluable due to its volume and number of specimens.

Over the past 20 to 30 years, the collection has been replenished with materials mainly from Türkiye. Samples belonging to 20 authors, including Kıyak and other researchers in his team, are kept in the Heteroptera collection as samples or references for species identification.

Highlights:

Collection materials have mostly been collected and described by Kıyak, and since 1985 many articles have been published on Türkiye's Heteroptera by Kıyak and Kıyak et al (See. References).

Research:

The ZMGU Heteroptera collection is used various research projects.

Because this collection specimens are important for the determination and description of Turkish Heteroptera fauna species.

They allow the study fauna of Türkiye are the basis for research in systematics, ecological and developmental biology, the study of historical changes of habitats or the study of the distribution history and current distribution of a species.

Specimens from different regions of the Türkiye or from different adjacent geographic regions can be compared.

The nomenclatural reviews of the taxa in the collection were arranged according to Aukema & Rieger (1995-2013).

The classification of identified all specimens in this collection into taxa is given and listed in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1. List of heteroptera species in Zoological Museum of Gazi University (ZMGU)

FAMILIA / GENUS	SPECIES
ACANTHOSOMATIDAE Signoret, 1864	
Elasmostethus Fieber, 1860	<i>Elasmostethus interstinctus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Elasmostethus minor</i> Horváth, 1899
ALYDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843	
Alydus Fabricius, 1803	<i>Alydus calcaratus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Camptopus Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Camptopus bifasciatus</i> Fieber, 1864
	<i>Camptopus illustris</i> Horváth, 1899
	<i>Camptopus lateralis</i> (Germar, 1817)
	<i>Camptopus tragacanthae</i> (Kolenati, 1845)
ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836	
Anthocoris Fallen, 1814	<i>Anthocoris nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)
	<i>Anthocoris pilosus</i> (Jakovlev, 1877)
Orius Wolff, 1811	<i>Orius laticollis</i> (Reuter, 1884)
	<i>Orius majusculus</i> (Reuter, 1879)
BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851	
Berytinus Kirkaldy, 1900	<i>Berytinus geniculatus</i> (Horvath, 1885)
	<i>Berytinus hirticornis nigrolineatus</i> (Jakovlev, 1903)
	<i>Berytinus minor</i> (Herrich-schaeffer, 1835)
	<i>Berytinus hirticornis pilipes</i> (Puton, 1875)
Metatropis Fieber, 1859	<i>Metatropis rufescens</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)
Neides Latreille, 1802	<i>Neides brevipennis</i> Puton, 1895
	<i>Neides tipularius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
COREIDAE Leach, 1815	
Anoplocerus Kiritshenko, 1926	<i>Anoplocerus luteus</i> (Fieber, 1861)
Arenocoris Hahn, 1834	<i>Arenocoris falleni</i> (Schilling, 1829)
	<i>Arenocoris waltlii</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)
Bathysolen Fieber, 1860	<i>Bathysolen nubilus</i> (Fallen, 1807)
Centrocoris Kolenati, 1845	<i>Centrocoris spiniger</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
	<i>Centrocoris variegatus</i> Kolenati, 1845
Ceraleptus A. Costa, 1847	<i>Ceraleptus lividus</i> Stein, 1858
	<i>Ceraleptus obtusus</i> (Brulle, 1839)
Coreus Fabricius, 1794	<i>Coreus marginatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)

Table 1. Continued...

Coriomeris Westwood, 1842	Coriomeris affinis (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1839)
	<i>Coriomeris denticulatus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
	<i>Coriomeris hirticornis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
	<i>Coriomeris subglaber</i> Horváth, 1917
Enoplops Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Enoplops disciger</i> (Kolenati, 1845)
	<i>Enoplops scapha</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
Gonocerus Berthold, 1827	<i>Gonocerus acuteangulatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Gonocerus juniperi</i> Herrich-Schaeffer, 1839
Haploprocta Stål, 1872	<i>Haploprocta sulcicornis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
	<i>Haploprocta umbrina</i> Jakovlev, 1883
Phyllomorpha Laporte, 1833	<i>Phyllomorpha laciniata</i> (Villers, 1789)
Spathocera Stein, 1860	<i>Spathocera dalmani</i> (Schilling, 1829)
	<i>Spathocera tenuicornis</i> Jakovev, 1883
Strobilotoma Fieber, 1860	<i>Strobilotoma typhaecornis</i> (Fabricius, 1803)
Syromastus Berthold, 1827	<i>Syromastus rhombeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)
CORIXIDAE Leach, 1815	
Corixa Geoffroy, 1762	<i>Corixa affinis</i> Leach, 1817
	<i>Corixa punctata</i> (Illiger, 1807)
Hesperocorixa Kirkaldy, 1908	<i>Hesperocorixa linnaei</i> (Fieber, 1848)
	<i>Hesperocorixa parallela</i> (Fieber, 1860)
Sigara Fabricius, 1775	<i>Sigara daghestanica</i> Jansson, 1983
	<i>Sigara lateralis</i> (Leach, 1817)
	<i>Sigara nigrolineata</i> (Fieber, 1848)
	<i>Sigara striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
CYDNIDAE Billberg, 1820	
Canthophorus Mulsant & Rey, 1866	<i>Canthophorus melanopterus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1835)
Cydnus Fabricius, 1803	<i>Cydnus aterrimus</i> (Forster, 1771)
Macroscytus Fieber, 1860	<i>Macroscytus brunneus</i> (Fabricius, 1803)
Ochetostethus Fieber, 1860	<i>Ochetostethus nanus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1834)
	<i>Ochetostethus sahlbergi</i> Wagner, 1952
Sehirus Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Sehirus morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)
Tritomegas Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Tritomegas bicolor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Tritomegas sexmaculatus</i> (Rambur, 1839)

Table 1. Continued...

GERRIDAE Leach, 1815	
Gerris Fabricius, 1794	<i>Gerris argentatus</i> Schummel, 1832
	<i>Gerris costae</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1850)
	<i>Gerris gibbifer</i> Schummel, 1832
	<i>Gerris lacustris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Gerris thoracicus</i> Schummel, 1832
Aquarius Schellenberg, 1800	<i>Aquarius ventralis</i> (Fieber, 1860)
	<i>Aquarius palludum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
HYDROMETRIDAE Billberg, 1820.	
Hydrometra Latreille, 1796	<i>Hydrometra stagnarum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
LEPTOPODIDAE Amyot and Serville, 1843	
Leptopus Latreille, 1809	<i>Leptopus marmoratus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829	
Aphanus Laporte, 1833	<i>Aphanus rolandri</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Apterola Mulsant & Rey, 1866	<i>Apterola lowni</i> (Saunders, 1876)
Beosus Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Beosus maritimus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
Brachyplax Fieber, 1860	<i>Brachyplax tenuis</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)
Callistonotus Horvath, 1906	<i>Callistonotus nigroruber</i> (Stål, 1859)
Camptotelus Fieber, 1860	<i>Camptotelus</i> sp.
Cymus Hahn, 1832	<i>Cymus simplex</i> Horvath, 1882
Diomphalus Fieber, 1864	<i>Diomphalus</i> sp.
Emblethis Fieber, 1860	<i>Emblethis bracynotus</i> (Horvat, 1897)
	<i>Emblethis denticollis</i> Horváth, 1878
	<i>Emblethis griseus</i> (Wolff, 1802)
Engistus Fieber, 1864	<i>Engistus</i> sp.
Gastrodes Westwood, 1840	<i>Gastrodes grossipes</i> (De Geer, 1773)
Geocoris Fallen, 1814	<i>Geocoris arenarius</i> (Jakovlev, 1867)
	<i>Geocoris erythrocephalus</i> (Lepelletier & Serville, 1825)
	<i>Geocoris pallidipennis</i> Costa 1843
	<i>Geocoris pubescens</i> (Jakovlev, 1871)
Gonianotus Fieber, 1860	<i>Gonianotus</i> sp.
Graptopeltus Stål, 1872	<i>Graptopeltus validus</i> (Horvath, 1875)
	<i>Graptopeltus lynceus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)
Heterogaster Schilling, 1829	<i>Heterogaster affinis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)
	<i>Heterogaster urticae</i> (Fabricius, 1775)

Table 1. Continued...

Icus Fieber, 1860	<i>Icus angularis</i> Fieber, 1861
Ischnodemus Fieber, 1837	<i>Ischnodemus suturalis</i> Horvath 1883
Ischnopeza Fieber, 1860	<i>Ischnopeza hirticornis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)
Lasiocoris Fieber, 1860	<i>Lasiocoris anomalus</i> (Kolenati, 1845)
	<i>Lasiocoris crassicornis</i> (Lucas, 1849)
Lethaeus Dallas, 1852	<i>Lethaeus fulvovarius</i> Puton, 1884
	<i>Lethaeus picipes</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)
Lygaeosoma, Spinola, 1837	<i>Lygaeosoma</i> sp.
	<i>Lygaeosoma sardeum sardeum</i> Spinola, 1837
Lygaeus Fabricius, 1794	<i>Lygaeus equestris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Macroplax Fieber, 1860	<i>Macroplax fasciata</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)
	<i>Macroplax preysleri</i> (Fieber, 1837)
Megalonotus Fieber, 1860	<i>Megalonotus chiragra</i> (Thomson, 1794)
	<i>Megalonotus setosus</i> Puton, 1874
Melanocoryphus Stål, 1872	<i>Melanocoryphus albomaculatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Melanocoryphus tristrami</i> (Douglas & Scott, 1868)
Horvatholus Josifov, 1965	<i>Horvathiolus superbus</i> (Pollich, 1781)
Metopoplax Fieber, 1860	<i>Metopoplax fuscinervis</i> Stal, 1872
Microplax Fieber, 1860	<i>Microplax interrupta</i> (Fieber, 1837)
	<i>Microplax limbata</i> Fieber, 1864
Nysius Dallas, 1852	<i>Nysius ericae</i> (Schilling, 1829)
	<i>Nysius cymoides</i> (Spinola, 1837)
	<i>Nysius graminicola</i> (Kolenati, 1845)
	<i>Nysius helveticus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)
	<i>Nysius thymi</i> (Wolff, 1804)
	<i>Nysius senecionis</i> (Schilling, 1829)
Ortholomus Stål, 1872	<i>Ortholomus punctipennis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)
Orsillus Dallas, 1852	<i>Orsillus depressus</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)
Oxycarenum Fieber, 1837	<i>Oxycarenum pallens</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)
Pachybrachius Hahn, 1826	<i>Pachybrachius fracticollis</i> (Schilling, 1829)
Paranysius Horvath, 1895	<i>Paranysius fraterculus</i> Horvath, 1895
Paraparomius, Harrington, 1980	<i>Paraparomius leptopoides</i> (Bärensprung, 1859)
Peritrechus Fieber, 1860	<i>Peritrechus geniculatus</i> (Hahn, 1832)
Perillus Stål, 1862	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)

Table 1. Continued...

Pezocoris Jakovlev, 1875	<i>Pezocoris apicimacula apicimacula</i> (A. Costa 1853)
	<i>Piezocoris minutus</i> (Jakovlev, 1874)
Pionosomus Fieber, 1860	<i>Pionosomus engizekicus</i> (Kıyak, 1995)
Proderus Fieber, 1860	<i>Proderus bellevoeyi</i> (Puton, 1873)
Rhyparochromus Hahn, 1826	<i>Rhyparochromus phoeniceus</i> (Rossi, 1794)
	<i>Rhyparochromus vulgaris</i> (Schilling, 1829)
	<i>Rhyparochromus pini</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Raglius Stål, 1872	<i>Raglius albaacuminatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Raglius confusus</i> (Reuter, 1886)
	<i>Raglius zarudyni</i> (Jakovlev, 1905)
Xanthochilus Stål, 1872	<i>Xanthochilus minusculus</i> (Reuter, 1885)
	<i>Xanthochilus saturnius</i> (Rossi, 1790)
Spilostethus Stål, 1868	<i>Spilostethus pandurus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
	<i>Spilostethus saxatilis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
Tropidothorax Bergroth, 1894	<i>Tropidothorax leucopteris</i> (Goeze, 1778)
MESOVELIDAE Douglas & Scott, 1867	
Mesovelia Malsant & Rey, 1852	<i>Mesovelia vittigera</i> Horváth, 1895
MICRONECTIDAE Douglas & Scott, 1867	
Micronecta Kirkaldy, 1897	<i>Micronecta anatolica anatolica</i> Lindberg, 1922
	<i>Micronecta griseola</i> Horváth, 1899
MIRIDAE Hahn, 1833	
Adelphocoris Reuter, 1896	<i>Adelphocoris bimaculicollis</i> Lindberg, 1948
	<i>Adelphocoris lineolatus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Adelphocoris vandalicus</i> (Rossi, 1790)
Alloeonotus Fieber, 1858	<i>Alloeonotus fulvipes</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
Aphanosoma A. Costa, 1842	<i>Aphanosoma italicum</i> A. Costa, 1842
Brachycoleus Fieber, 1858	<i>Brachycoleus decolor</i> Reuter, 1887
Calocoris Fieber, 1858	<i>Calocoris affinis</i> (Herrich-schaeffer, 1835)
	<i>Calocoris norvegicus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)
	<i>Calocoris roseomaculatus</i> (De Geer, 1773)
Closterotomus Fieber, 1858	<i>Closterotomus reuteri</i> (Horvath, 1882)
Camponotidea Reuter, 1879	<i>Camponotidea fieberi</i> Reuter, 1879
	<i>Camponotidea saundersi</i> (Puton, 1874)

Table 1. Continued...

Horistus Fieber, 1860	<i>Horistus bimaculatus</i> (Jakovlev, 1884)
	<i>Horistus orientalis</i> (Gimelin, 1790)
	<i>Horistus infuscatus</i> (Brulle, 1832)
Chargochilus, Fieber 1858	<i>Chargochilus gyllenhali</i> (Fallén, 1807)
Chlamydatus Curtis, 1833	<i>Chlamydatus pullus</i> (Reuter, 1870)
Cranocapsus Wagner, 1954	<i>Cranocapsus turcicus</i> Kıyak, 1990
Cyphodema Fieber, 1858	<i>Cyphodema cilicica</i> Seidenstücker, 1954
	<i>Cyphodema instabilis</i> (Lucas, 1849)
	<i>Cyphodema mendosa</i> Montandon, 1887
Deraeocoris Kirschbaum, 1856	<i>Deraeocoris punctum</i> (Rambur, 1839)
	<i>Deraeocoris rutilus</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1838)
	<i>Deraeocoris trifasciatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)
	<i>Deraeocoris ventralis</i> Reuter, 1904
Dicyphus Fieber, 1858	<i>Dicyphus montandoni</i> Reuter, 1888
Dimorphocoris Reuter, 1890	<i>Dimorphocoris distylus</i> Seidenstücker, 1964
Eurycolpus Reuter, 1875	<i>Eurycolpus aureolus</i> Seidenstücker, 1961
Globiceps Lepeletier & Serville, 1825	<i>Globiceps flavomaculatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
	<i>Globiceps horvathi</i> Reuter, 1912
Grypocoris Douglas & Scott, 1868	<i>Grypocoris amoneus</i> (Douglas & Scott, 1868)
	<i>Grypocoris fieberi</i> Douglas & Scot, 1868
	<i>Grypocoris heinzi</i> Wagner, 1966
	<i>Grypocoris melanopygus</i> Horvath, 1906
Halticus Hahn, 1832	<i>Halticus pusillus</i> (Herrich-Scaeffler, 1835)
Leptopterna Fieber 1858	<i>Leptoterna dolobrata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Liocoris Fieber, 1858	<i>Liocoris tripustulatus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
Lygocoris Reuter, 1875	<i>Lygocoris pernicioides</i> Seidenstücker, 1957
	<i>Lygocoris rugicollis</i> (Fallen, 1807)
Lygus Hahn, 1833	<i>Lygus gemellatus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)
	<i>Lygus rugulipennis</i> (Poppius, 1911)
	<i>Lygus pratensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Megalocelous Reuter, 1890	<i>Megalocelous hungaricus</i> Wagner E., 1944
	<i>Megalocoleus molliculus</i> (Fallén, 1807)
	<i>Megalocoleus tanaceti</i> (fallen 1807)
Myrmecoris Gorski, 1852	<i>Myrmecoris gracilis</i> (R.F. Sahlberg, 1848)
Notostira Fieber, 1858	<i>Notostira erratica</i> (Linné, 1758)

Table 1. Continued...

Oncotylus Fieber, 1858	<i>Oncotylus viridiflavus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Oncotylus setulosus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1837)
Opisthotaenia Reuter, 1901	<i>Opisthotaenia fulvipes</i> Reuter, 1901
Orthocephalus Fieber, 1858	<i>Orthocephalus melas</i> Seidenstücker, 1962
	<i>Orthocephalus fulvipes</i> Reuter, 1904
Piezocranum Horvath, 1877	<i>Piezocranum corvinum</i> Puton, 1895
Plagiotylus Scott, 1874	<i>Plagiotylus dispar</i> Reuter, 1899
Poecilonotus Reuter, 1896	<i>Poecilonotus picturatus</i> (Reuter, 1896)
Polymerus Hahn, 1831	<i>Polymerus unifasciatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
Psallus Fieber, 1858	<i>Psallus ocularis</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)
Rhabdomiris Wagner, 1968	<i>Rhabdomiris striatellus striatellus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
Stenodema Laporte, 1833	<i>Stenodema calcarata</i> (Fallen, 1807)
	<i>Stenodema laevigata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Stenotus Jakovlev, 1877	<i>Stenotus binotatus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
NABIDAE A. Costa, 1853	
Himacerus Wolff, 1811	<i>Himacerus apterus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)
	<i>Himacerus mirmicoides</i> (A. Costa, 1834)
Nabis Latreille, 1802	<i>Nabis capsiformis</i> Germar, 1838
	<i>Nabis ferus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Nabis limbatus</i> Dahlbom, 1851
	<i>Nabis pseudoferus</i> Remane, 1949
	<i>Nabis punctatus</i> A. Costa, 1847
	<i>Nabis rugosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Nabis viridilus</i> Spinola, 1837
NAUCORIDAE Leach, 1815	
Ilyocoris Stål, 1861	<i>Ilyocoris cimicoides</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
NEPIDAE Latreille, 1802	
Nepa Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Nepa</i> sp. Linnaeus, 1758
NOTONECTIDAE Leach, 1815	
Anisops Spinola, 1837	<i>Anisops debilis perplexus</i> Poisson, 1929
	<i>Anisops sardeus sardeus</i> Herrich-Schäffer, 1849
Notonecta Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Notonecta glauca</i> Linnaeus, 1758
	<i>Notonecta maculata</i> Fabricius, 1794

Table 1. Continued...

Notonecta Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Notonecta obliqua</i> Thunberg, 1787
	<i>Notonecta viridis</i> Delcourt, 1909
OCHTERIDAE Kirkaldy, 1906	
Ochterus Latreille, 1807	<i>Ochterus marginatus marginatus</i> (Latreille, 1804)
PENTATOMIDAE Leach, 1815	
Acrosternum Fieber, 1860	<i>Acrosternum heegeri</i> Fieber, 1861
Aelia Fabricius, 1803	<i>Aelia acuminata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Aelia albovittata</i> Fieber, 1868
	<i>Aelia sibirica</i> Reuter, 1884
	<i>Aelia rostrata</i> Boheman, 1852
	<i>Aelia virgata</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1841)
Ancyrosoma Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Ancyrosoma leucogrammes</i> (Gmelin, 1790)
Antheminia Mulsant & Rey, 1866	<i>Antheminia absinthii</i> (Wagner, 1952)
	<i>Antheminia lunulata</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Antheminia pusio</i> (Kolenati, 1846)
Apodiphus Spinola, 1837	<i>Apodiphus amygdali</i> (Germar, 1817)
Arma Hahn, 1832	<i>Arma insperta</i> Horvath, 1899
Bagrada Stål, 1862	<i>Bagrada stolidus</i> (Herrich & Schaffer, 1839)
Carpocoris Kolenati, 1846	<i>Carpocoris fuscispinus</i> (Boheman, 1851)
	<i>Carpocoris mediterraneus mediterraneus</i> Tamanini, 1958
	<i>Carpocoris melanocerus</i> (Mulsant & Rey, 1852)
	<i>Carpocoris pudicus</i> (Poda, 1761)
	<i>Carpocoris purpureipennis</i> (De Geer, 1773)
Cnephosa Jakovlev, 1880	<i>Cnephosa flavomarginata</i> Jakovlev, 1880
Codophila Mulsant & Rey, 1866	<i>Codophila varia</i> (Fabricius, 1787)
Crypsinus Dohrn, 1860	<i>Crypsinus</i> sp.
Derula Mulsant & Rey, 1856	<i>Derula flavoguttata</i> Mulsant & Rey, 1856
Dolycoris Mulsant & Rey, 1866	<i>Dolycoris baccarum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Dyroderes Spinola, 1837	<i>Dyroderes umbraculatus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)
Eurydema Laporte, 1833	<i>Eurydema blanda</i> Horvath, 1903
	<i>Eurydema fieberi</i> Schummel, 1837
	<i>Eurydema putoni</i> (Jakovlev, 1887)
	<i>Eurydema olarecea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)

Table 1. Continued...

Eurydema Laporte, 1833	<i>Eurydema ornata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Eurydema rugulosa</i> (Dohrn, 1860)
	<i>Eurydema ventralis</i> Kolenati, 1846
Eysarcoris Hahn, 1834	<i>Eysarcoris aeneus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
	<i>Eysarcoris ventralis</i> (Westwood, 1837)
Graphosoma Laporte, 1833	<i>Graphosoma consimile</i> Horvath, 1903
	<i>Graphosoma lineatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Graphosoma melanoxanthum</i> Horvath, 1903
	<i>Graphosoma semipunctatum</i> (Fabricius, 1775)
Holcogaster Fieber, 1860	<i>Holcogaster fibulata</i> (Germar, 1831)
Holcostethus Fieber, 1860	<i>Holcostethus albipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
	<i>Holcostethus strictus vernalis</i> (Wolff, 1804)
Jalla Hahn, 1832	<i>Jalla dumosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Leprosoma Baerensprung, 1859	<i>Leprosoma tuberculatum</i> Jakovlev, 1874
Mustha Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Mustha spinosula</i> (Lefebvre, 1831)
Neottiglossa W. Kirby, 1837	<i>Neottiglossa flavomarginata</i> (Lucas, 1849)
	<i>Neottiglossa leporina</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1830)
	<i>Neottiglossa pusilla</i> (Gmelin, 1790)
Nezara Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Nezara viridula</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Palomena Mulsant & Rey, 1866	<i>Palomena prasina</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)
Pausias Jakovlev, 1905	<i>Pausias martini</i> (Puton, 1890)
Peribalus Mulsant & Rey	<i>Peribalus strictus vernalis</i> (Wolff, 1804)
Perillus Stål, 1862	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)
Picromerus Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Picromerus bidens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Picromerus nigridens</i> (Fabricius, 1803)
Piezodorus Fieber, 1860	<i>Piezodorus lituratus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
Raphigaster Laporte, 1833	<i>Raphigaster nebulosa</i> (Poda, 1761)
Risibia Horváth, 1888	<i>Risibia christophi</i> (Jakovlev, 1886)
Rhombocoris, Mayr, 1864	<i>Rhombocoris</i> sp.
Sciocoris Fallen, 1829	<i>Sciocoris cursitans</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
	<i>Sciocoris distinctus</i> Fieber, 1851
	<i>Sciocoris helferi</i> Fieber, 1851
	<i>Sciocoris homalonotus</i> Fieber, 1851
	<i>Sciocoris luteolus</i> Fieber, 1861
	<i>Sciocoris macrocephalus</i> Fieber, 1851

Table 1. Continued...

Sciocoris Fallen, 1829	<i>Sciocoris ochraceus</i> (Fieber, 1861)
	<i>Sciocoris pallens</i> Klug, 1845
	<i>Sciocoris pictus</i> Wagner, 1959
	<i>Sciocoris sulcatus</i> Fieber, 1851
Stagonomus Gorski, 1852	<i>Stagonomus amoneus</i> (Brulle, 1832)
	<i>Stagonomus bipunctatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Staria Dohrn, 1860	<i>Staria lunata</i> (Hahn, 1835)
Tarisa Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Tarisa osmanica</i> Hoberlandt, 1956
Tholagmus Stål, 1860	<i>Tholagmus flavolineatus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)
Trochiscocoris Reuter, 1890	<i>Trochiscocoris rotundatus</i> Horvath, 1895
Ventocoris Hahn, 1834	<i>Ventocoris rusticus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
Vilpianus Stål, 1860	<i>Vilpianus galii</i> (Wolff, 1802)
Zicrona Amyot & Serville, 1843	<i>Zicrona caerulea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
PLATASPIDAE Dallas, 1851	
Coptosoma Laporte, 1833	<i>Coptosoma scutellatum</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)
PLEIDAE Fieber, 1853	
Plea Leach, 1817	<i>Plea minutissima minutissima</i> Leach, 1817
PYRRHOCORIAE Amyot & Serville, 1843	
Pyrrhocoris Fallen, 1814	<i>Pyrrhocoris apterus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Pyrrhocoris marginatus</i> (Kolenati, 1845)
Scantius Stål, 1866	<i>Scantius aegyptius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
REDUVIIDAE Latreille, 1807	
Coranus Curtis, 1833	<i>Coranus aegyptius</i> (Fabricius, 1775)
	<i>Coranus contrarius</i> Reuter, 1881
	<i>Coranus niger</i> (Rambur, 1840)
Holotrichius Burmeister, 1835	<i>Holotrichius denudatus</i> (A. Costa, 1842)
Nagusta Stål, 1859	<i>Nagusta goedeli</i> (Kolenati, 1857)
Oncocephalus Klug, 1830	<i>Oncocephalus pilicornis</i> Reuter, 1882
	<i>Oncocephalus squalidus</i> (Rossi, 1790)
	<i>Oncocephalus thoracicus</i> Fieber, 1861
Phymata Latreille, 1802	<i>Phymata crassipes</i> (Fabricius, 1775)
Peirates Serville, 1831	<i>Peirates hybridus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
Reduvius Fabricius, 1775	<i>Reduvius pallipes</i> Klug, 1830
	<i>Reduvius testaceus</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1845)

Table 1. Continued...

Rhynocoris Hahn, 1833	<i>Rhynocoris annulatus</i> ssp. <i>annulatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Rhynocoris erytropus</i> (Linne, 1767)
	<i>Rhynocoris ibericus</i> (Kolenati, 1857)
	<i>Rhynocoris iracundus</i> (Poda, 1761)
	<i>Rhynocoris punctiventris</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1846)
Sphedanolestes Stål, 1867	<i>Sphedanolestes pulchellus</i> (Klug, 1830)
Zelus Fabricius, 1803	<i>Zelus renardii</i> (Kolenati, 1857)
RHOPALIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843	
Agraphopus Stål, 1872	<i>Agraphopus suturalis</i> Reuter, 1900
Brachycarenum Fieber, 1860	<i>Brachycarenum languidus</i> (Horvath, 1891)
	<i>Brachycarenum tigrinnus</i> (Schilling, 1829)
Chorosoma Curtis, 1830	<i>Chorosoma schillingii</i> (Schilling, 1829)
Corizus Fallen, 1814	<i>Corizus brevicarnis</i> Horváth, 1917
	<i>Corizus hyosciami hyosciami</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Corizus hyosciami nigridorsum</i> (Puton, 1874)
Liorhyssus Stål, 1870	<i>Liorhyssus hyalinus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
Maccevethus Dallas, 1852	<i>Maccevethus caucasicus</i> (Kolenati, 1845)
	<i>Maccevethus errans</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
	<i>Maccevethus corsicus corsicus</i> Signoret, 1862
	<i>Maccevethus corsicus persicus</i> Jakovlev, 1882
Rhopalus Schilling, 1827	<i>Rhopalus conspersus</i> (Fieber, 1837)
	<i>Rhopalus lepidus</i> Fieber, 1861
	<i>Rhopalus maculatus</i> (Fieber, 1837)
	<i>Rhopalus parumpunctatus</i> (Schilling, 1829)
	<i>Rhopalus rufus</i> Schilling, 1829
	<i>Rhopalus subrufus</i> (Gmelin, 1790)
Stictopleurus Stål, 1872	<i>Stictopleurus abutilion</i> (Rossi, 1790)
	<i>Stictopleurus crassicornis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Stictopleurus pictus</i> (Fieber, 1861)
	<i>Stictopleurus subtomentotus</i> (Rey ,1888)
SALDIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843	
Saldula Van Duzee, 1914	<i>Saldula fucicola</i> (J. Sahlberg, 1870)
	<i>Saldula pallipes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)
	<i>Saldula saltatoria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
Macrosaldula Leston & Southwood, 1964	<i>Macrosaldula variabilis</i> (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)

Table 1. Continued...

SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815	
Eurygaster Laporte, 1833	<i>Eurygaster dilaticolis</i> Dohrn, 1860
	<i>Eurygaster hottentotta</i> (Fabricius, 1775)
	<i>Eurygaster integriceps</i> Puton, 1881
	<i>Eurygaster maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Eurygaster testudinaria</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)
Odontoscelis Laporte, 1833	<i>Odontoscelis dorsalis</i> (Fabricius, 1798)
	<i>Odontoscelis fuliginosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)
	<i>Odontoscelis lineola</i> Rambur, 1839
Odontotarsus Laporte, 1833	<i>Odontotarsus impictus</i> Jakovlev, 1886
	<i>Odontotarsus plicatulus</i> Horvath, 1906
	<i>Odontotarsus purpureolineatus</i> (Rossi, 1790)
	<i>Odontotarsus robustus</i> Jakovlev, 1884
	<i>Odontotarsus rufescens</i> Fieber, 1861
Psacasta Germar, 1839	<i>Psacasta cypria</i> (Puton, 1881)
STENOCEPHALIDAE Dallas, 1852	
Dicranocephalus Hahn, 1826	<i>Dicranocephalus agilis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)
	<i>Dicranocephalus albipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)
	<i>Dicranocephalus setulosus</i> (Ferrari, 1874)
TINGIDAE Laporte, 1832	
Catoplatus Spinola, 1837	<i>Catoplatus anticus ssp. anticus</i> Reuter, 1880
	<i>Catoplatus carthusianus</i> (Goeze, 1778)
	<i>Catoplatus hilaris</i> (Horvath, 1906)
	<i>Catoplatus horvathi</i> (Puton, 1878)
	<i>Catoplatus nigriceps</i> Horváth, 1905
Copium Thunberg, 1822	<i>Copium brevicorne</i> (Jakovlev, 1879)
	<i>Copium teucrüi teucrüi</i> (Host, 1788)
Dictyla Stål, 1874	<i>Dictyla echü</i> (Schränk, 1782)
	<i>Dictyla nassata</i> (Puton, 1874)
	<i>Dictyla triconula</i> (Seidenstrücker, 1954)
Elasmotropis Stål, 1874	<i>Elasmotropis testacea testacea</i> (Herrich-Schäffer, 1830)
Monosteira A. Costa, 1862	<i>Monosteira lobulifera</i> (Reuter, 1888)
Tingis Fabricius, 1803	<i>Tingis cardui cardui</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
	<i>Tingis ciliaris</i> Puton, 1879

Table 1. Continued...

Tingis Fabricius, 1803	<i>Tingis elongata</i> (Fieber, 1861)
	<i>Tingis grisea</i> Germar, 1835
VELIIADE Brullé, 1836	
Velia Latreille, 1804	<i>Velia affinis filippii</i> Tamanini, 1947
	<i>Velia caprai</i> Tamanini, 1947

CONCLUSION

Most of the heteroptera specimens in the Zoology museum of Gazi University consist of diagnosed specimens (Table 1).

These examples of field studies conducted since 1985 from various regions of Türkiye research projects, studies and / or were collected during the thesis work.

However, there are still undiagnosed samples.

Most of the specimens have been included in collections as dry and needled specimens. Some material is preserved in alcohol jars.

The numbers of identified taxa in this collection is given in the table below (Table 2, Figure 1).

Table 2. Numbers taxa of Heteroptera collection in ZMGU

	Families	Genera	Species group
Taxa	30	204	381

Figure 1. Numbers taxa of Heteroptera collection in ZMGU

Table 3.Numbers taxa of Heteroptera collection in ZMGU in Türkiye.

	Türkiye	ZMGU
Familia	40	30
Genera	420	204
Species/Subspecies	1540	381

Figure 2. Numbers taxa of Heteroptera collection in ZMGU in Türkiye.

As can be seen from the table 2, 204 genera and 381 species-group belonging to 30 families are preserved in the ZMGU museum (Table 2, Figure 1, 2).

Türkiye Heteroptera fauna is represented by 420 genera and 1540 species of 40 families (Önder, et al., 2006; (Önder, et al., 2006; Dursun et al, 2010; Fent et al. 2010; Kıyak & Akar 2010; Çerçi & Dursun, 2017; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Özgen & Çerçi, 2018; Çerçi & Gözüaçık, 2019; Çerçi et al., 2019, 2020, 2021; Çerçi & Koçak, 2017; Çerçi, 2021; Çerçi & Tezcan, 2020; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi & Oruz, 2021), (Table 2, Figure 1, 2).

Accordingly, 24.7% of species group taxa, 48.5% of genus taxa and 75% of family taxa are available in our museum collection.

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